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Effect of Lead Mining on the Arterial Blood Pressure of Mining Workers in Ameka Ezza South, Ebonyi State

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the arterial blood pressure effects of lead exposure on workers in the lead mining industry particularly in Ameka Ezza South, Ebonyi State. Lead, a toxic metal, has been linked to various health complications, particularly cardiovascular issues. This research aims to assess the impact of lead mining on the heart health of workers by analyzing the relationship between blood lead levels (BLLs) and cardiovascular conditions. A cross-sectional study was conducted at lead mining site in Ameka Ezza South Local Government Area, Ebonyi State involving both current and former workers with varying exposure durations. Blood lead concentrations were measured using atomic absorption spectrometry, while cardiovascular health was assessed through automatic sphygmomanometer, stethoscope, metallic jelly. Additionally, workers completed questionnaires regarding their work history and health status. Statistical analysis was performed to identify correlations between lead exposure and cardiovascular health outcomes. The results indicate a strong link between higher lead exposure and an increased risk of cardiovascular problems such as hypertension, increased atherosclerosis, endothelial dysfunction and arrhythmias. These findings highlight the need for enhanced safety protocols in lead mining operations to reduce workers' exposure and prevent long-term cardiovascular health risks. Regular health

monitoring and protective measures are crucial to safeguard workers' well-being.

Keywords:- *absorption spectrometry, endothelial dysfunction, sphygmomanometer, hypertension*

INTRODUCTION

According to the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR), lead is the second most hazardous substance. Metallic lead (Pb0) is a bluish-gray heavy metal, resistant to corrosion because, when it is exposed to air or water, thin films of lead compounds (oxides and carbonates) are formed and protect this metal from further attacks [7].

It is a ubiquitously distributed environmental toxicant that is naturally present in the earth cortex, but anthropogenic activities are responsible for its widespread in all compartments of the environment. The phasing out of leaded gasoline for vehicles between 1973 and 1995 and the removal of the metal from paint by 1978 have resulted in a substantial lowering of mean blood lead levels (BLL). However, because Pb²⁺ is a persistent metal, it is still present in all compartments of the environment, water, soil, and dust, making human exposure to occur via food, water, air, and soil (Gupta, 2016; Patrick, 2006). However it is made up of two major components; Tin and Antimony but present in several minerals, but according to international Agency for research on cancer IARC(2006), all are of minor significance except the sulfide PbS called Glenna or lead glance, which is the major source of lead production throughout the world. Lead is also found in anglesite (PbSO₄) and cerussite (PbCO₃).

It is the most important toxic heavy element in the environment due to its important physio-chemical properties, its

use can be retraced to historical times. Globally it is abundantly distributed, yet dangerous environmental chemical (Mahaffay, 1990). Its important properties like softness, malleability, ductility, poor conductivity and resistance to corrosion seem to make difficult to give up on its use due to its non-biodegradable nature ,continuous use and its concentration.

The cardiovascular system is critical for maintaining overall health, and disturbances in its function can lead to severe health consequences, including hypertension, atherosclerosis, and increased risk of cardiovascular events such as heart attacks and strokes (Hedge *et al.*, 2020). Evidence suggests that even low levels of lead exposure can have harmful effects, contributing to elevated blood pressure and promoting endothelial dysfunction(Cook *et al.*, 2022).

This study aims to explore the mechanisms through which lead affects cardiovascular health, examining both acute and chronic exposure scenarios. Understanding these effects is essential for developing effective intervention strategies and regulatory policies to protect vulnerable populations, particularly workers in lead-intensive environments in Abakaliki metropolis [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

- Electrocardiogram machine
- Questionnaire
- Automatic sphygmomanometer
- Stethoscope
- Ethical approval letter

- Cotton wool
- Hand gloves
- 70% alcohol
- Metallic jelly
- Consent letter

STUDY AREA

This research was carried out at lead miming site, Ameka in Ezza local Government Area, Ebonyi State.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

Age Range: Specific age groups 18-65 years

Non-smokers, non-alcoholics. Characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, or socioeconomic status.

Geographic Location: Participants from specific regions or community.

Exclusion Criteria:

Comorbid Conditions: Certain health issues that may interfere with the study e.g., stroke, cardiovascular disease severe mental illness etc.

Pregnancy: Often excluded in studies involving medications or certain treatments.

Consent form was given to each participants to indicate their voluntary

Inability to Provide Consent: Individuals who cannot give informed consent due to cognitive impairment were not included.

CONSENT FORM

Agreement to take part in the study. It outlines important information, such as the purpose of the research, what participation involves, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and the right to withdraw at any time. The form ensures that participants are fully informed and agree to the terms before engaging.

POPULATION SIZE

20 individuals consented to the research and was used for the research.

QUESTIONNAIRE

A well-organized questionnaire was used for the research to gather information on personal data, medical status was presented in the work place and blood pressure measurement was carried out on them to ascertain the effect of the lead mining on them.

DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical package for social science (spss) was used to analyze the data and present it in Mean ± SEM and P value less than 0.01 were considered significant.

RESULTS

Table 1:-Showing the effect of lead mining on the systolic and diastolic blood pressure of workers in Ameka Ezza South, Ebonyi state at $P \geq 0.01$

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	P-Value
Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) (mmHg)	90-99	1	5.26	0.254
	100-109	2	10.52	
	110-119	3	15.79	
	120-129	4	21.05	

	130-139	9	47.37	
	≥140	0	0	
Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) (mmHg)	40-49	1	5.26	0.254
	50-59	4	21.05	
	60-69	2	10.52	
	70-79	10	52.65	
	80-89	2	10.52	
	≥90	0	0	

Fig.1:-Showing graphical presentation of the systolic blood pressure of the study participant which shows a significant increase in % as against the systolic values.

Fig.2:-Showing graphical presentation of the diastolic blood pressure of the study of participants which shows a significant increase in % range from 40-59 and a decrease in 60-69, then increase in 70-79 and decrease in 80-89 of diastolic values.

DISCUSSION

The association between systolic and diastolic blood pressure on the cardiovascular effect of lead exposure on the mining workers in Ameka Ezza South, Ebonyi state metropolis was significant with a $p > 0.01$ which is in line with the work done by Gambelunghé [2]; even after adjustment for potential confounders such as age, sex, smoking habits, alcohol intake and educational level.

According to Huang (2022)), the relationship between blood lead levels with systolic and diastolic pressure is positive but no significant effect associated with blood lead levels and hypertension indicating that this present study align with the previous findings.

By analyzing a national cohort of the NHANES III participants for a period of 18 year of follow-up (1988 to 2010), our results demonstrate that as the blood lead levels increases the risk of dying from cardiovascular diseases becomes higher. This result is supported by other studies that have demonstrated a positive association of lead exposure with cardiovascular risk factors and CVD mortality [1,3].

The pathophysiology of lead-induced hypertension has been explored in numerous studies. According to Vaziri [6], proposed mechanisms include dysregulation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, direct effects on the endothelium and vascular smooth muscle, and activation of the sympathetic nervous system due to increased catecholamine production. Many of these effects may be mediated through oxidative stress, which can be generated directly by lead ions or through lead's binding to glutathione, disrupting one of the body's key defenses against reactive oxygen species. Lead's impact on the endothelium is particularly notable as it binds to and inhibits

endothelial nitric oxide synthase, thereby reducing nitric oxide production and impairing vasodilation.[5].

CONCLUSION

The results indicate a strong link between higher lead exposure and an increased risk of cardiovascular problems such as the association between systolic and diastolic blood pressure on the cardiovascular effect of lead exposure on the mining workers in Ameka Ezza South, Ebonyi state metropolis was significant with a $p > 0.01$

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